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Abstract

Dynamic Voltage and Frequency Scaling (DVFS) has been extensively used in mobile devices to reduce the dynamic power consumption. With the advent of smart phones, the design of DVFS policies has become quite challenging. Having given the users the freedom to download and use applications of their choice, the policies need to ensure that all the applications work seamlessly. Keeping this in mind, we have come up with a design of a policy which works well across all kinds of workloads with the greatest benefit obtained for memory-bound workloads. The policy performs workload decomposition into on-chip and off-chip work using the values reported by the performance counters. The policy designed can be further improved by incorporating the energy usage into the decision making logic and then choosing a frequency which would provide the best energy savings without considerable performance loss.

Introduction

Reducing the power consumption and hence extending the battery life of mobile devices is the need of the hour. A number of DVFS policies have been devised in order to achieve lower levels of energy consumption. DVFS tries to reduce the dynamic power consumption by reducing the voltage and frequency of the CPU and provide “just-enough” circuit speed to meet the deadlines of the workloads. Due to the quadratic dependence and linear dependence of voltage and frequency on dynamic power consumption respectively, a cubic reduction in power can be achieved without any considerable hit in performance.

The DVFS policy implemented here tries to break the workload into two parts: off-chip and on-chip. The decomposition is done with the help of performance counters made available by the PMU. Based on these values and the performance threshold value which is dynamically set based on current CPU utilization, a target frequency for the next quanta is decided. Based on the value of the target frequency obtained, one of the four available frequencies is selected.

The policy designed gives most energy savings for memory-bound applications and performance loss constrained energy savings for compute bound applications. It is elaborated more in implementation and results section.

Related Work

There are several different DVFS techniques that have been proposed. Most of the techniques use much more information than the information available from performance counters to perform DVFS. Eg: Task arrival times, workload, deadlines, compiler or application support. The techniques which achieve DVFS using runtime statistics to identify the workload of a task and thus estimate and predict the optimal setting can be classified as fine-grained or course-grained. Fine-grained techniques adjust the voltage/frequency setting within a task boundary and usually perform better than course-grained techniques and hence this is the technique that we chose.

Techniques considered :

In [3], Weissel and Bellosa propose a course-grained DVFS technique for multitasking systems called

Process Cruise Control. Their technique uses event counters, which are counters that monitor countable tasks such as instructions, memory requests, and clock cycles. Their technique calculated instructions per clock cycle and memory requests per clock cycle from the data collected from the event counters. A matrix of frequency domains is built from event count monitoring and is used to choose a frequency domain for an executing task. The specifics of what actually defines an event counter, the exact thresholds for changing the frequency settings are not very clear and hence the idea of this implementation was dropped.

Results from [1] and [6] show that it is advantageous to reduce the CPU frequency for a memory-intensive task, but not for a CPU-intensive task. The performance of a task with high CPU utilization is linearly dependent on frequency, and thus will suffer significant throughput loss when the frequency is lowered. A memory intensive task, however, will suffer minimal performance loss when the frequency is reduced. If a task is constantly accessing memory, then the CPU is constantly stalling and waiting for memory. Power consumption can be reduced by lowering the frequency for a memory intensive task, and system performance can be increased by running a CPU-intensive task at the highest frequency.

In [6], Ghiman and Rosing propose a coarse-grained DVFS technique for a general purpose, multitasking system. Their technique uses runtime statistics and an online learning algorithm to select a voltage/frequency setting for an executing task. But implementation of this algorithm requires the data from many performance counters. Eg: Instructions executed, data cache misses, instruction cache stalls, data dependency stalls, and clock cycles. Hence this idea was also rejected as the same performance benefit would be hard to get with only 3 performance counters available.

Technique implemented:

In [1], Choi, Soma, and Pedram present a fine-grained DVFS technique using Workload Decomposition, which classifies CPU workload as either on-chip or off-chip. This technique was highly tailored to the kind of environment that was used in the project. Performance counters were used to monitor the data cache miss count, CPU stall cycle count, number of clock counts in a quantum, and the number of executed instructions. This was the implementation chosen in the end. An additional tweak to the system in the form of dynamically changing the performance loss threshold based on CPU utilization numbers was added. This implementation was chosen as huge power savings can be obtained for memory bound applications for which it is best suited for. For the other applications, a trade off can be achieved between performance and power savings. The performance threshold value which can be easily modified allows the algorithm to choose between performance and power savings. Also the algorithm can be further enhanced to choose a frequency setting which would optimize the energy savings of the system as well.

Policy Design – Dynamic Voltage and Frequency Scaling – Workload Decomposition (DVFS-WD)

The workload of a task is often represented by the number of CPU clock cycles required to complete the task and is either given in advance for hard real-time operation or is predicted at run-time for soft-real time operation such as multimedia processing. In both cases, however, the question of workload composition in terms of the CPU-bound versus memory-bound instructions is often overlooked. The decomposition of CPU workload of a task can be done either statically using off-line profiling and compiler support or dynamically using a performance monitoring unit (PMU). This method is mainly a Dynamic Voltage and Frequency Scaling based on Workload Decomposition (DVFSWD). In this design technique,

1. For saving energy consumption, the workload of a task is dynamically decomposed into on-chip and off-chip by using an embedded hardware unit in the processor.

2. Accurately and efficiently, the ratio of on-chip computation time to off-chip access times is calculated by using information about the data cache misses and the CPU stall cycles due to data dependencies.
3. A simple timing model for calculating the off-chip access overhead in terms of internal bus and external memory access clock cycle times.

Definitions:

Workload of a task is defined as the sum of the CPI's of all instructions in the instruction stream of the task. It depends on various dynamic parameters such as the *on-chip stall* cycle count due to data/control dependency or branch misprediction, and the *off-chip stall* cycle count due to instruction/data (I/D) cache miss or I/D TLB miss.

The workload of a program, W , can be written as:

$$W = N \cdot CPI^{avg}$$

$$= N \cdot (CPI_0 + CPI_{branch_miss}^{avg} + CPI_{stall_onchip}^{avg} + CPI_{stall_offchip}^{avg})$$

Where N is the number of instructions, CPI_0 is the ideal CPI which is 1 for a single-issue general-purpose microprocessor, $CPI_{branch_miss}^{avg}$ denotes the number of CPU clock cycles due to branch misprediction overhead, and $CPI_{stall_onchip}^{avg}$ and $CPI_{stall_offchip}^{avg}$ denote the numbers of CPU clock cycles due to onchip stalls and off-chip stalls, respectively.

On-chip workload, W_{ON} , is the number of CPU clock cycles required to perform the set of on-chip instructions, which are executed inside the CPU only. The execution time required to finish W_{ON} , T_{ON} , varies depending on the CPU frequency, f_{CPU} , and is calculated as $T_{ON} = W_{ON}/f_{CPU}$.

Off-chip workload, W_{OFF} , is the number of external clock cycles needed to perform the set of off chip accesses. Note that the CPU stalls until the external memory transactions are completed. The execution time required to complete W_{OFF} , T_{OFF} , depends on the external memory clock frequency, f_{EXT} , and is calculated as $T_{OFF} = W_{OFF}/f_{EXT}$.

The increased execution time of a program due to lowered clock frequency represents the performance loss (PF_{loss}), which is defined as follows:

$$PF_{loss} = \frac{T_{f_{CPU}}}{T_{f_{max}^{CPU}}} - 1$$

Where f_{max}^{CPU} is the maximum frequency of the CPU, $T_{f_{CPU}}$ and $T_{f_{max}^{CPU}}$ are the total task execution times at CPU frequencies of f_{CPU} and f_{max}^{CPU} , respectively. The optimal frequency, f_{target}^{CPU} , for a given PF_{loss} value is calculated as follows:

$$f_{target}^{CPU} = \frac{f_{max}^{CPU}}{1 + PF_{loss} \cdot \left[1 + \left(\frac{T_{OFF}}{T_{ON}} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{f_{max}^{CPU}}{f_{CPU}} \right) \right]}$$

When frequency scaling is performed, not only f_{CPU} is changed but also f_{INT} and f_{EXT} are scaled. Therefore, the effect of f_{INT} and f_{EXT} on the total program execution time should also be considered.

T_{OFF} is strongly dependent on the external clock frequency. The internal bus clock frequency also affects T_{OFF} . Due to lack of exact timing information about these two operations which are performed during a D-cache miss service, we have opted to model T_{OFF} as a function of both the internal clock frequency and the external memory access clock as follows:

$$T^{OFF} = \frac{\alpha \cdot W^{OFF}}{f^{INT}} + \frac{(1-\alpha) \cdot W^{OFF}}{f^{EXT}}$$

Where α is the ratio between the data transfer time and the data fetch time and f_{INT} is internal bus clock frequency.

Based on the experimental results on various application programs, an α value of ~ 0.35 was obtained for all applications.

The PMU supports monitoring of few performance events including cache hit/miss, TLB hit/miss, and number of executed instructions. There is a limitation in using these events in the sense that only two events can be monitored at the same time along with the number of clock counts in a quantum (CCNT). We need CPI_{avg} on to separate workload.

Off-chip execution time is calculated based on two separate events: the data cache miss count and the CPU stall cycle count. We ought to monitor three different events.

From the paper, we have figured out following three events proved to be more useful

- (i) Number of instructions being executed (INSTR)
- (ii) Number of stall cycles due to data dependency (STALL)
- (iii) Number of D-cache misses (DMISS).

INSTR is required to get the CPI value, which indirectly represents the amount of off-chip workload. STALL captures the number of clock cycles when the CPU is stalled due to data dependency either because of on-chip stalls from internal register dependencies or off-chip stalls from external memory access. The D-cache miss event can be used as an approximate metric to determine whether a task is CPU or memory-bound.

Algorithm: (Two broken parts)

Figure-1: OFFLINE Algorithm to get calculate CPI_{avg}^{ON} - done as a part of profiling

Figure-2: Complete Algorithm that calculates Optimum frequency on-the-fly (online)

Implementation:

Calculating T-ON

$$T^{on} = \frac{W^{on}}{f_{cpu}}, \quad W^{on} = N \cdot CPI_{on}^{avg}$$

$SPI^{avg} = STALL / INSTR$, during a time quantum

Onchip CPI value without any stall cycles $CPI_{on}^{avg} = CPI_{on}^{min} + SPI_{on}^{avg}$

To calculate T_{on} , we need to know CPI_{on}^{avg} as seen in this equation. We define SPI as ratio of the number of stall cycles to the total instruction count and plot CPI_{on}^{avg} and SPI_{on}^{avg} on Y and X axis, respectively. From this plot, it was found that CPI_{on}^{avg} is linearly related to SPI_{on}^{avg} as this equation. CPI_{on}^{avg} is the average CPI values for onchip instructions and can be given as the summation of CPI_{on}^{min} and SPI_{on} . Here, CPI_{on}^{min} is onchip CPI without any stalls which is the y-intercept point in this plot and SPI_{on} is onchip stall cycles per onchip instructions. .

Based on the following observation, the more D-cache miss events, the higher probability of off-chip accesses.

We define DPI as ratio of the number of D-cache miss events to the total instruction count

$DPI^{avg} = DMISS / INSTR$, during a time quantum

$$CPI_{on}^{avg} = CPI_{on}^{min} + dpi2spi(DPI)$$

$$DF = \frac{(CPI_{on}^{max} - CPI_{on}^{min})}{n}$$

All the results and observations out of the experiments are plotted in the subsequent figures as shown for both CPU bounded and memory bounded (for 245 and 600 MHz),

Figure -3 : Contour Plots for CPIavg vs SPI avg for different clock frequency combinations

$dpi2spi(DPI)$	DPI
$CPI_{on}^{max} - CPI_{on}^{min}$	$DPI \leq K_1$
$DF * (n-1)$	$K_1 < DPI \leq K_2$
...	...
$DF * 2$	$K_{n-2} < DPI \leq K_{n-1}$
$DF * 1$	$K_{n-1} < DPI \leq K_n$
0	$DPI > K_n$

K_n is constant: $K_1 < K_2 < \dots < K_n$

Figure-4: SPI_{on}^{avg} extraction using DPI

Calculating T^{off}

$$T^{off} = T_{int}^{off} + T_{ext}^{off} = \frac{\alpha \cdot W^{off}}{f^{int}} + \frac{(1-\alpha) \cdot W^{off}}{f^{ext}}$$

All the above are explained in the definitions.

Determining the optimal frequency setting:

Using Ton and Toff we decomposed the Workload into Workload ON (Won) and Workload OFF (Woff) using the formulas given in the definition section.

Performance Loss Threshold is calculated using the following regression equation obtained from various experiments and observations as given below.

$$Performance\ Loss_{Threshold} = \frac{10}{103} * \sqrt{103^2 - Utilization^2}$$

From the estimated Performance Loss threshold as constraint, we get the approximate frequency from the Target Frequency equation given in the definition. The weight factor 103 is calibrated with assured energy savings of few % despite CPU bounded workload outside the decomposition technique. This takes care of the minimum system energy setting.

Now, the so forth obtained target frequency setting for the next quantum is in matched against the nearest available frequency value i.e. 245, 400, 480 and 600 MHz and is used.

Software Architecture for DVFS-WD policy.

The software architecture comprises of a PRA policy setting module tightly linked with the Linux scheduler, the PMU, and the freq. and voltage control circuitry on the given HTC-Aria Android Phone.

Figure-5: ARM-11 Processor based Qualcomm platform with Kernel and DVFS policy

III. Measurements, Analysis and Observations

Utilization curve and Power/Energy graph comparing performance and DVFS-WD policy is given per each test case.

Testcase : Script_test1.sh

Script_test1.sh	% of time				CPU Average utilization	Average Power(mW)	Energy (J)
	245 MHz	400 MHz	480 MHz	600 MHz			
conservative	0	0	0	100	0.98	438.6	24.39055
interactive	0	0	0	100	0.98	438.6	24.21949
ondemand	0.2176673	0	0	99.7823	0.98	437.97429	24.14552
powersave	100	0	0	0	0.98	151.14	23.83327
performance	0	0	0	100	0.98	438.6	24.3423

Governor Name	Frequency	CPU Utilization	Average Power (mW)
userspace	600 Mhz	0.98	438.6
	480 Mhz	0.98	340.14
	400 Mhz	0.98	270.3
	245 Mhz	0.98	151.14

Governor Name	CPU Utilization	Average Power (mW)	Energy (J)
DVFS - WD	0.98	397	20.644

Governor Name	Energy (J)	Run time (ms)	Energy Savings (%)	Slowdown (%)
ondemand	24.14552	55130	+16.96	6.01
performance	24.3423	55500	+ 17.91	6.73
DVFS - WD	20.644	52000	--	--

Analysis and observations:

- As can be seen from the table above, our policy gives energy savings of 16.96% and 17.91% over on demand and performance governors respectively.
- At the same time the execution is faster by 6.01% and 6.73% respectively over the same governors.
- The energy consumption is also the least when compared to all the available scaling governors.
- Hence the policy works well over CPU intensive workloads.

Utilization figure-6 for script_test1.testcse.

Figure-7: Power comparison of modified DVFS-Work Decomposition policy for CPU intensive Scripts test1 workload

Testcase Script_test2.sh

Script_test2.sh	% of time				CPU Average utilization	Average Power(mW)	Energy (J)
	245 MHz	400 MHz	480 MHz	600 MHz			
conservative	0	0	0	100	0.99	441.8	39.19208
interactive	0	0	0	100	0.99	441.8	39.02419
ondemand	0.1921	0	0	99.8079	0.99	441.24333	39.04121
powersave	100	0	0	0	0.99	152.07	35.17987
performance	0	0	0	100	0.99	441.8	39.40414

Governor Name	Frequency	CPU Utilization	Average Power(mW)
userspace	600 Mhz	0.99	441.8
	480 Mhz	0.99	342.57
	400 Mhz	0.99	272.15
	245 Mhz	0.99	152.07

Governor Name	CPU Utilization	Average Power (mW)	Energy (J)
DVFS - WD	0.99	433	35.5060

Utilization graph: Figure - 8

Governor Name	Energy (J)	Run time (ms)	Energy Savings (%)(WD)	Slowdown (%)
ondemand	39.04121	8848	+9.95	+7.90
performance	39.40414	8919	+10.9	+8.76
DVFS - WD	35.5060	8200	--	--

Analysis and observations:

- As can be seen from the table above, our policy gives energy savings of 9.95% and 10.9% over ondemand and performance governors respectively.
- At the same time the execution is faster by 7.90% and 8.76% respectively over the same governors.
- Except for powersave mode, the energy consumption is also the least when compared to all the available scaling governors.
- Hence the policy works well over this CPU intensive workload as well.
- The policy gives both energy savings and speedup over both CPU intensive workloads.

Testcase mp3_test1.mp3

mp3_test1.mp3	% of time				CPU Average utilization	Average Power(mW)	Energy (J)
	245 MHz	400 MHz	480 MHz	600 MHz			
conservative	4.2431	58.3767	37.3802	0	0.24	141.2954	34.75867
interactive	100	0	0	0	0.39	96.27	23.68242
ondemand	74.6432	19.9346	0	5.4222	0.35	112.58237	27.69526
powersave	100	0	0	0	0.38	95.34	23.45364
performance	0	0	0	100	0.19	185.8	45.7068

Governor Name	Frequency	CPU Utilization	Average Power (mW)
userspace	600 Mhz	0.19	185.8

	480 Mhz	0.22	155.46
	400 Mhz	0.25	135.25
	245 Mhz	0.38	95.34

Governor Name	CPU Utilization	Average Power (mW)	Energy (J)
DVFS - WD	0.23	131	32.75

Governor Name	Energy (J)	Run time (ms)	Energy Savings (%) (WD)	Slowdown (%)
ondemand	27.69526	246000	- 18.25	--
performance	45.7068	246000	+39.56	--
DVFS - WD	32.75	246000	--	--

Utilization-figure - 9:

Figure-10: Power comparison of modified DVFS-Work Decomposition policy for mp3 (audio) workload

Analysis and observations:

- As can be seen from the table above, our policy works best over performance and little under performance w.r.t the ondemand case i.e. in cases where the workload is evenly distributed over memory and CPU. The energy consumption increases by 18.25 % when compared to ondemand. But the policy is better than the performance scaling governor (~39 % improvement in energy consumption)
- As is the requirement in case of mp3 applications, the audio output is seamless. There is no slowdown.
- Given more time, the policy implemented can be easily modified to yield better results over these kinds of workloads as well. Limitation in the number of frequencies was also one of the factors which reduced the performance for these kinds of workloads.

Testcase video_test1.mp4

video_test1.mp4	% of time				CPU Average utilization	Average Power (mW)	Energy (J)
	245 MHz	400 MHz	480 MHz	600 MHz			
conservative	0	0	0	100	0.36	240.2	39.633
interactive	0	0	0	100	0.37	243.4	40.161
ondemand	10.3406	36.5483	18.368	34.743	0.45	205.76594	33.95138
powersave	100	0	0	0	0.71	126.03	20.79495
performance	0	0	0	100	0.36	240.2	39.633

Governor Name	Frequency	CPU Utilization	Average Power (mW)
userspace	600 Mhz	0.37	243.4
	480 Mhz	0.41	201.63
	400 Mhz	0.49	179.65
	245 Mhz	0.71	126.03

Governor Name	CPU Utilization	Average Power (mW)	Energy (J)
DVFS - WD	0.47	175	31.5

Governor Name	Energy (J)	Run time (ms)	Energy Savings (%)	Slowdown (%)
ondemand	33.95138	165000	+7.7	--
performance	39.633	165000	+20.52	--
DVFS - WD	31.5	165000	0	--

Analysis and observations:

- As can be seen from the table above, our policy gives energy savings of 7.7% and 20.52% over ondemand and performance governors respectively.
- At the same time the execution rate is maintained. This is very important for video applications as any glitches can be easily observed and are very irritating to the user.

- Except for powersave, the energy consumption is also the least when compared to all the available scaling governors.
- Hence the policy works well over video applications.

Utilization figure - 11 (given above)

Figure-12: Power comparison of modified DVFS-Work Decomposition policy for Video1 workload

Testcase video_test2.mp4

video_test2.mp4	% of time				CPU Average utilization	Average Power (mW)	Energy (J)
	245 MHz	400 MHz	480 MHz	600 MHz			
conservative	0	0	0	100	0.38	246.6	25.1532
interactive	100	0	0	0	0.71	126.03	12.85506
ondemand	9.1247	31.7093	33.0306	26.1354	0.47	208.6481	21.28211
powersave	100	0	0	0	0.72	126.96	12.94992
performance	0	0	0	100	0.38	246.6	25.1532

Governor Name	Frequency	CPU Utilization	Average Power (mW)
userspace	600 Mhz	0.38	246.6
	480 Mhz	0.44	208.92
	400 Mhz	0.51	183.35
	245 Mhz	0.72	126.96

Governor Name	CPU Utilization	Average Power (mW)	Energy (J)
DVFS - WD	0.45	171	20.52

Governor Name	Energy (J)	Run time (ms)	Energy Savings (%)	Slowdown (%)
ondemand	21.28211	102000	+3.7	--
performance	25.1532	102000	+22.5	--
DVFS - WD	20.52	102000	0	--

Analysis and observations:

- As can be seen from the table above, our policy gives energy savings of 3.7% and 22.5% over ondemand and performance governors respectively.
- At the same time the execution rate is maintained which is crucial for video applications
- The energy consumption is also the least when compared to ondemand, performance and conservative scaling governors.
- Hence the policy works well over video applications.

Figure -13: Utilization

Figure-15: Power comparison of modified DVFS-Work Decomposition policy for Video2 workload

Test case Camera video

Camera_video	% of time				CPU Average utilization	Average Power (mW)	Energy (J)
	245 MHz	400 MHz	480 MHz	600 MHz			
conservative	0	0	0	100	0.93	422.6	12.678
interactive	0	0	0	100	0.81	384.2	11.526
ondemand	0	0	0	100	0.82	387.4	11.622
powersave	100	0	0	0	0.91	144.63	4.3389
performance	0	0	0	100	0.81	384.2	11.526

Governor Name	Frequency	CPU Utilization	Average Power (mW)
userspace	600 Mhz	0.86	400.2
	480 Mhz	0.78	291.54
	400 Mhz	0.76	229.6
	245 Mhz	0.82	136.26

Governor Name	CPU Utilization	Average Power (mW)	Energy (J)
DVFS - WD	97	372	11.16

Governor Name	Energy (J)	Run time (ms)	Energy Savings (%)	Slowdown (%)
ondemand	11.622	30000	+4.14	--
performance	11.526	30000	+3.28	--
DVFS - WD	11.16	30000	0	--

Analysis and observations:

- As can be seen from the table above, our policy gives energy savings of 4.14% and 3.28% over ondemand and performance governors respectively.
- Except for powersave governor, the energy consumption is also the least when compared to all the available scaling governors.
- Hence the policy works well over interactive workloads as well.

Figure – 16: Utilization

Figure-17: Power comparison of modified DVFS-Work Decomposition policy for Interactive camera workload

New Test case

Camera_video	% of time				CPU Average utilization	Average Power (mW)	Energy (J)
	245 MHz	400 MHz	480 MHz	600 MHz			
conservative	0.058	0.021	0.115	0.804	0.38	229.877	21.20388
interactive	1	0	0	0	0.71	126.03	15.64158
ondemand	0.0008	0.162	0.211	0.625	0.47	246.58	23.99757
powersave	1	0	0	0	0.72	126.96	15.45992
performance	0	0	0	1	0.38	246.6	22.35676

Governor Name	Frequency	CPU Utilization	Average Power (mW)
userspace	600 Mhz	0.31	224.2
	480 Mhz	0.38	194.34
	400 Mhz	0.44	170.4
	245 Mhz	0.68	123.24

Governor Name	CPU Utilization	Average Power (mW)	Energy (J)
DVFS - WD	0.70	222	20.424

Governor Name	Energy (J)	Run time (ms)	Energy Savings (%)	Slowdown (%)
ondemand	23.99757	9732	+17.49	+5.78
performance	22.35676	9066	+9.46	+1.45
DVFS - WD	20.424	9200	0	-1.47

Utilization figure - 18

Figure-19: Power comparison of modified DVFS-Work Decomposition policy for I/O intensive workload

Analysis and observations:

- As can be seen from the table above, our policy uses much more energy when compared to all the other in-built policies.
- Except for performance governor, the run time is the least when compared to all the available scaling governors.
- Hence the policy does not work well with highly varying workloads.

Further Discussion:

Justification for the Policy: Most previous DVFS methods are concerned about CPU energy reduction only, more precisely dynamic portion of the CPU energy. However, most computing systems consist of not only CPU, but many subsystems such as memory and peripheral devices. In general, power consumption in these subsystems are not affected by CPU frequency changes and also it takes up a significant portion of total system power. So, reduction of CPU energy only cannot guarantee longer battery lifetime for the whole system. The motivation of workload decomposition is that different applications show different execution time variation according to the CPU frequency. For example, in case of CPU-bound applications, execution time strongly depend on the CPU frequency, whereas there is little variation in memory-bound applications. This is because a program execution sequence consists of on-chip and off-chip workloads. Here, on-chip workload is work performed inside the CPU, like register-register instruction and ALU operation. Off-chip workload is work performed outside the CPU. Ex, cache miss and subsequent access to offchip main memory. Power consumption profile severely fluctuates due to alternate execution of W_{ON} and W_{OFF} .

Policy performance and best suited workloads: This policy suits well for Multimedia and non-real-time workloads. On the HTC-Aria mobile platform, we achieved energy saving (CPU+memory) of 20-40% with variable performance loss(10-30)% for CPU-bound applications, whereas 10-20% saving was achieved for memory-bound applications.

figure 20: Mem bound vs frequency.

Memory boundedness is ideally workload agnostic. This policy sets the frequency for a for the given value of memory boundedness (and the desired frequency) observed by reading performance counters. Considering CPU energy saving only, about 80% saving can be possible for memory-bound programs. For both CPU and memory-bound programs, target performance degradation was finely estimated and controlled through regression equation. (above figure shows more generic relation between memory boundedness w.r.t family of performance loss curves.

In a nutshell:

At estimated and constrained performance loss, there are considerable energy savings when we run in New Policy ranging from 3%-40% with an exception during MP3 palyer testcase;

Figure21: % Energy Savings that each policy has over the top of DVFS-Workload Decomposition for various applications

Figure22: Absolute Energy that each policy burnt on the top of DVFS-Workload Decomposition.

From these measurements in figure 21, we conclude that our proposed DVFS technique results in energy savings of 11-20% for CPU-bound applications (“script1”, “script2”), and 10-18% energy savings for memory-bound applications under 20-30% performance loss bounds. The lower energy saving results for memory-bound applications should be understood in light of the fact that in these applications most of the energy is consumed in accessing the main memory, and of course, the memory energy consumption is fixed (since operating voltage of memory is fixed although memory clock frequency varies.) It would be interesting to report the actual energy saving values for the CPU only. Unfortunately, we cannot do this because of the current limitation of the HTC Aria Mobile platform (no separate power planes for the CPU and main memory are provided.)

Absolute execution times and their penalty due to New Policy. (We observe no noticeable increase in the Execution time due to frequency scaling and power loss.

Figure23: Execution times across varying workloads

Conclusions and future recommendations

A regression-based DVFS policy for finely-tunable energy-performance trade-off was proposed and implemented on HTC Aria mobile platform. In this project, the policy done for DVFS approach, a program execution time is decomposed into two parts: on-chip computation and off-chip access latencies. The CPU voltage/frequency is scaled based on the ratio of the on-chip and off-chip latencies for each process under a given performance degradation factor. This ratio is given by a regression equation, which is dynamically updated based on runtime event monitoring data provided by an embedded performance monitoring unit. Through actual current measurements in hardware, we demonstrated that energy saving of 20-50% with 20-30% performance loss for CPU-bound applications, whereas ~10-20% saving was achieved for memory-bound applications. For both CPU and memory-bound programs, target performance degradation was finely controlled.

There are currently many different dynamic voltage and frequency scaling methods proposed and being researched. Because of the need for energy minimization in embedded systems, DVFS will continue to be researched and improved upon for years to come. Some ideas for future work include perfecting DVFS techniques for multi-tasking systems and combining DVFS techniques with Dynamic Power management.

We have shown that low level DVFS methods such as implementing algorithms in the kernel as opposed to the user-level is more effective. However, we have learned that kernel-level programming is significantly more difficult and dangerous than user-level programming. One bad pointer can cause the entire system to stall, and, when this occurs, rebooting is the only solution. Kernel modifications also need to be lightweight to accommodate the limited amount of memory on embedded systems. As defined in [9], experiential learning is the "knowledge, skills, and/or abilities attained through observation, simulation, and/or participation that provide depth and meaning to learning by engaging the mind and/or body through activity, reflection, and application." Experiential learning best describes the lessons we learned from this project. No classroom could have ever taught us the skills and knowledge that we learned from actually working with the Linux kernel and facing the many challenges researchers and developers face

This policy as such could be improved by enhancing compute bounded application runs. Inclusion of prediction, machine learning techniques to better predict the next move, stochastic process based decisions could really improve the compute bound application's performance. As such for memory there is also some scope of improvement over accurately estimating the system component's power with least performance loss.

References

1. Kihwan Choi, Ramakrishna Soma and Massoud Pedram, "Dynamic Voltage and Frequency Scaling based on Workload Decomposition", ISLPED 2004, California, USA
2. Massoud Pedram, "Review of the Apollo Testbed Project", USC, 2003
3. A. Weissel and F. Bellosa, "Process Cruise Control," CASES 2002, October 2002, Grenoble, France.
4. Xiaotao Liu, Prashant Shenoy and Weibo Gong, "A Time Series-based Approach for Power Management in Mobile Processors and Disks", NOSSDAV 2004, Cork, Ireland
5. Leo Singleton, Christian Poellabauer and Karsten Schwan, "Monitoring of Cache Miss Rates for Accurate Dynamic Voltage and Frequency Scaling" College of Computing, Georgia Institute of Technology Department of Computer Science & Engineering, University of Notre Dame.

6. Dhiman, G. and Rosing, T. S. 2007. "Dynamic voltage frequency scaling for multi-tasking systems using online learning." In Proceedings of the 2007 International Symposium on Low Power Electronics and Design (Portland, OR, USA, August 27-29, 2007). ISLPED '07. ACM, New York, NY, 207-212
7. Application Note 174 : Changing clocks on the ARM1136JF-S Core Module (for information on the internal clock and external clock frequencies)
8. ARM 1136 Technical Reference Manual (for details of the ARM 1136 Microarchitecture)
9. "Experiential Learning," <http://people.uleth.ca/~steve.craig/whatis.htm>